

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF $ZnCo_2O_4$ NANOPARTICLES BY REVERSE MICELLE PROCESSING

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Abstract

Nanostructured spinel $ZnCo_2O_4$ (20–30 nm) was synthesized by reverse micelle processing the mixed precursor (consisting of $Co(NO_3)_3$ and $Zn(NO_3)_2$). The average size of the particles increases with increasing water to surfactant molar ratio. The Fourier transform infrared spectra also confirm the formation $ZnCo_2O_4$. Magnetization study reveals that the $ZnCo_2O_4$ sample exhibits superparamagnetic behavior. The transformation of the mixed precursor into nano structured spinel $ZnCo_2O_4$ upon calcinations was confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurement, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM).

1. Introduction

The synthesis of nano-crystalline spinel has been investigated intensively due to the unique potential applications of nano-crystalline spinels in high density magnetic recording and microwave devices, magnetic fluids, and also as an absorbent material to remove sulfide gases from hot-coal gas [1] and [2]. Spinel-type pigments are commonly used for decorating porcelain and other ceramic products. The spinels are complex oxides and represented by the general formula of $A^{2+}B^{3+}O_4$. The common methods reported for the synthesis of cobalt zinc are sol-gel, EDTA chelating precursor [4], combustion [5] and [6], polymerized complex [7], glycine chelated precursor [8], hydrothermal [9], molten salt [10], polymer aerosol pyrolysis [11], and reverse micelle processes [12]. $ZnCo_2O_4$ nanopowders prepared by the reverse micelle process. The aim of the present work is to prepare

$ZnCo_2O_4$ nanopowders and study their structural and magnetic properties. A tertiary reverse microemulsion system was used to synthesize these nanocrystals. The influence of water to surfactant ratio on the particle size has been studied, since it plays a vital role in controlling the droplet size and hence the size of the crystal. Also, readily available, inexpensive and easy handling precursors have been used in the present study and that eliminates the extra handling requirements associated with the moisture sensitive precursors.

2. Experiment

$Co(NO_3)_3$ and $Zn(NO_3)_2$ were used as the precursors of cobalt oxide and zinc, respectively. An aqueous solution of the precursors was prepared by dissolving $Zn(NO_3)_2$ (0.1 M) and $Co(NO_3)_3$ (0.2 M) in distilled water to a molar ratio of 1:2. Cyclohexane (Sigma Aldrich) was used as the solvent. Reverse microemulsion was prepared by mixing 40 mL of nonionic surfactant (poly(oxyethylene) nonylphenyl ether, Igepal CO-520, Aldrich, USA), 100 ml of cyclohexane and 6.5–13 ml of mixed aqueous solution (Zn : Co = 1 : 2). The microemulsion was stirred vigorously, and after 5 min of equilibration, 5–10 ml of NH_4OH (28%) (Dae Jung chemicals, Korea) was injected into the microemulsion. The particles were subsequently washed using ethanol to remove any residual surfactant.

The thermal characteristics of the powders were determined by thermogravimetry (TG) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) techniques (SCINCO, STA 1500). The phase identification of calcined powders was carried out by X-ray diffractometer (Philips X'pert MPD 3040). The

particle size of the calcined powders was analyzed using Transmission electron microscope (TEM) operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV (JEOL, JEM 2100F).

3. Results and discussion

Ternary systems of Cyclohexane/Igepal CO 520/water offer certain advantages: they are spheroidal and monodisperse aggregates where water is readily solubilized in the polar core, forming a ‘water pool’ characterized by the ratio of water to surfactant concentration. Another important property of reverse micelles is their dynamics character; the water pools can exchange their contents by a collision process. The aggregation and self-assembly of the oil/surfactant/water species is complex, and very little is known about the cluster growth and final nanostructure as a function of synthesis conditions. The molar ratio of water to surfactant can determine the size of the microemulsion water core[13]. Therefore, the diameter of the nanoparticles in the microemulsion can be controlled by the water/surfactants molar ratio(R) and Zn molar ratio($x=0.4$) at aqueous solution value. In this present study we have chosen $x=0.4$ because magnetic moment decreased as the concentration of increased to $x=0.5$ due to lattice perfection which is caused by increased number of Zn ions on the A site, as result of according as interaction increases with spin of B site by magnetic moment of A site is weak, magnetic moment is decreased that semi-balance ingredient is grown[14].

The XRD patterns of the calcined powders are shown in Fig. 1. Extremely broad peaks are observed and those indicate the presence of very fine particles. The observed diffraction peaks correspond to the standard patterns of $ZnCo_2O_4$ spinel (JCPDS Card No. 23-1390). No other crystalline phases are found in the calcined samples. The broadening of XRD peaks increases as the water to surfactant ratio is decreased for the preparation of powder. The crystallite size of powders is obtained using different water to surfactant ratio. The average crystallite size of the powders increases as the water to surfactant ratio (R) is increased from 4 to 8 during the preparation of powder.

Fig.1. X-ray diffraction patterns of powders calcinations at 400°C for 5h as a function of R(water /surfactants molar ratio).

Fig.2 shows the transmission electron microscopy of the synthesized $ZnCo_2O_4$ particles. It has been shown that the average size of the synthesized powder are about 10-20nm and synthesized $ZnCo_2O_4$ particles size and distribution increased from 4 to 8 with increased R .

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs of the synthesized $ZnCo_2O_4$ nanoparticles calcined at 600°C for 5h by a reverse micelle process: a) $R=4$, b) $R=6$ and c) $R=8$

Fig.3. show magnetic properties of the ZnCo_2O_4 particles as a function of R. From the VSM analysis, the synthesized nanosized crystalline powder exhibiting superparamagnetic properties.

Fig. 3. Magnetic properties of the synthesized ZnCo_2O_4 powders calcinations at 600°C for 2 h as a function of R (water /surfactants molar ratio).

4. Conclusions

Nanosized ZnCo_2O_4 powders have been prepared using a reverse micelle process. The water/surfactants molar ratio at aqueous solution value influenced the average size and

distribution of the synthesized particles. The average size and size distribution of the synthesized particles was about 10-20nm and broaden, respectively. Reverse micelle synthesis of ZnCo_2O_4 powders yields a nanosized crystalline powder exhibiting superparamagnetic character. The saturation magnetization of synthesized ZnCo_2O_4 powders were below 30(emu/g). It is possible to the application of magnetic nanoparticles for drug delivery using nanoparticulate magnetic carrier. If the water/ surfactant molar ratio and mixture ratio of the aqueous solutions(Zn concentration) is carefully controlled, it is possible to control the average size, crystalline phase and magnetic property of the synthesized powders.

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